
APPENDIX **A**

Vehicle modelization

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Supporting information for

The transport of goods in the urban environment: a comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Electric, Compressed Natural Gas and Diesel light-duty vehicles

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

1015: Japanese 10-15 mode driving cycle

AER: All Electric Range

AMDC: Artemis Motorway Driving Cycle

ARDC: Artemis Road Driving Cycle

BOM: Bill Of Materials

BU: Battery Usage

CO₂: Carbon dioxide

DP: Dynamic Programming

D1: 1.7 L Euro 5 GM prototype Diesel engine

D2: 1.3 L Euro 5 GM prototype Diesel engine

181

EM: Electric Machine
EoL: End of Life
EPD: Environmental Product Declaration
EV: Electric Vehicle
EWC: European Waste Catalogue
FC: Fuel consumption
FD: Final Drive
FU: Functional Unit
GB: Gear Box
GM: General Motors
GWP: Global Warming Potential
GVW: Gross Vehicle Weight
HEV: Hybrid Electric Vehicle
ICEV: Internal Combustion Engine Vehicle
IMDS: International Material Data System
LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
LCV: Light Commercial Vehicle
NO_x: Nitrogen oxides
OEM: Original Equipment Manufacturer
PF: Power Flow
PG: Planetary Gear set
SO₂: Sulphur dioxide
SOC: State Of Charge
TKM: Kilometres travelled
TR: Transmission
VMT: Vehicle Miles Travelled
VOC: Volatile Organic Compound
WLTP: Worldwide harmonized Light vehicle Test Procedures
WTW: Well-To-Wheel
WHTC: World Harmonized Transient Cycle

Variables

C: Cost [\$]
C_{bat}: Battery capacity [Ah]
E: Energy [J]
I_{bat}: Battery current [A]
J: Objective function [-]
N_{in}: Number of time intervals [-]
P_v: Vehicle power [W]
R_{wh}: Dynamic radius of the wheel [m]
t: Time [s]
T: Torque [Nm]
u: control strategy
V_v: Velocity [m/s]

Greek symbols

- α : Sub-control variable of PF
- λ : Battery life consumption [Ah]
- Λ : Battery life [Ah]
- σ : Severity factor for battery aging [-]
- τ_{gb} : Speed ratio of the single-speed gearbox [-]
- τ_{pg} : Speed ratio of the planetary gearset [-]
- ω : Angular speed [rad/s]

1. LCI: Life Cycle Inventory

The stage Life cycle inventory has been carried out inserting in the SimaPro software (version 8.2) all the material and energy flows entering the system boundary. SimaPro is an LCA software developed by *Pré Consultants*. It contains many different databases (EcoInvent 3, Agri-footprint, ETH-ESU 96, Franklin USA 98 IDEMAT 2001, Industry Data, LCA Food DK, USA Input Output Database 99) composed of datasets, describing materials production, transports, processes, etc.... with these software and datasets it is possible to build the entire production chain of the product under analysis and its life cycle. In this study for secondary data, we used the EcoInvent database, by the eponim Swiss research centre, composed by the École Polytechnique Fédérale De Lausanne (EPFL), the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich (ETH Zurich), Empa research centre (*Material Science and Technology*), the Institute for natural and engineering sciences Paul Scherrer (PSI), the database can be updated and integrated by the users. End of life scenarios can be modelled, it is possible to evaluate and compare the impacts of the dataset created by the user.

1.1 Components production

The “*components production*” processes include all the stages related to the production of vehicle components (UP from 1 to 6) and their transport to the manufacturing plants. The OEM provided a bill of materials comped of almost 2.000 parts for each of the three configuration. To model such an amount of data, components have been split in big charismatic components (batteries, motors, engines, etc. ...) for whom an ad hoc datasets have been created, the rest of the components are considered as a sum of materials and the weight of their VDA materials has been aggregated and treated as a single component. OEM provided the list of the components for each vehicle. Using the IMDS it was possible to obtain the material composition of every component. Due to the number of the components (more than 2000) it was not possible to model every single component. So two different strategies have been adopted:

- Complex components: in this group are included all the relevant component, composed of many materials or that require particular manufacturing processes (e.g. battery, engines, ...), for each of these components a specific dataset has been created in the software, using the composition provided by the IMDS and looking for literature information about their manufacturing process, or using already made datasets from EcoInvent;
- Simple components: it groups all the components composed of one or two materials and that do not require specific manufacturing processes. These components composed of the

same material and undergoing the same manufacturing process have been grouped and modelled as a single component, with the same mass as the sum of the masses of each component.

In the next paragraph is described the way simple components and some of the most relevant complex components have been modelled. In the following paragraph the inventory of processes from 1 to 6 will be presented. For some components the sole VDA composition was considered too wide for the modelization. In these cases, through the IMDS, the elemental composition of the components is investigated and the composition is modelled in deeper detail. It happens when the VDA category is not considered precise enough for the environmental modelization (e.g. VDA category “other materials and compound”).

1.1.1 Simple Components

The classification of materials in the IMDS is the VDA classification. The VDA classification is from the German Association of the Automotive Industry. It is composed of 9 macro-groups of materials commonly used in automotive, and their subgroups (see table below).

Table 20. VDA Classification

1 Steels and iron materials
1.1 Steels/Cast steel/ Sintered steel
1.1.1 Unalloyed, low alloyed
1.1.2 Highly alloyed
1.2 Cast iron
1.2.1 Cast iron with lamellar graphite / tempered cast iron
1.2.2 Cast iron with lamellar graphite / tempered cast iron
1.2.3 Highly alloyed cast iron
2 Light alloys, cast and wrought alloys
2.1 Aluminium and aluminium alloys
2.1.1 Cast aluminium alloys
2.1.2 Wrought aluminium alloys
2.2 Magnesium and magnesium alloys
2.2.1 Cast magnesium alloys
2.2.2 Wrought magnesium alloys
2.3 Titanium and titanium alloys
3 Heavy metals, cast and wrought alloys
3.1 Copper (e.g. copper amounts in cable harnesses)
3.2 Copper alloys
3.3 Zinc alloys
3.4 Nickel alloys
3.5 Lead
4 Special metals
4.1 Platinum / rhodium
4.2 Other special metals
5 Polymer materials

5.1 Thermoplastics
5.1.a filled Thermoplastics
5.1.b unfilled Thermoplastics
5.2 Thermoplastic elastomers
5.3 Elastomers / elastomeric compounds
5.4 Duromers
5.4.1 Polyurethane
5.4.2 Unsaturated polyester
5.4.3 Other duromers
5.5 Polymeric compounds (e.g. inseparable laminated trim parts)
5.5.1 Plastics (in polymeric compounds)
5.5.2 Textiles (in polymeric compounds)
6 Process polymers
6.1 Lacquers
6.2 Adhesives, sealants
6.3 Underseal
7 Other materials and material compounds (scope of mixture)
7.1 Modified organic natural materials (e.g. leather, wood, cardboard)
7.2 Ceramics / glass
7.3 Other compounds (e.g. friction linings)
8 Electronics / electrics
8.1 Electronics (e.g. pc boards, displays)
8.2 Electrics
9 Fuels and auxiliary means
9.1 Fuels
9.2 Lubricants
9.3 Brake fluid
9.4 Coolant / other glycols
9.5 Refrigerant
9.6 Washing water, battery acids
9.7 Preservative
9.8 Other fuels and auxiliary means

Based on this classification, we built the datasets for these groups in SimaPro. To model some VDA classes considered too generic, through the IMDS has been analysed the elemental composition of the components included in the specific VDA class. For example, if the class 1.1 Steels/Cast steel/ Sintered steel includes only low alloyed steel, the VDA Class 1.1 Steels/Cast steel/ Sintered steel is modelled at 100% like low alloyed steel. In the following tables, the datasheets of the VDA subgroups are listed.

1 Steels and iron materials

Table 21. 1.1 “Steels/Cast steel/ Sintered steel”.

1	kg	1.1 Steels/Cast steel/Sintered steel
1	kg	Casting, steel, lost-wax {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for steel product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

Table 22. 1.1.1 “Unalloyed/Low alloyed”

1	kg	1.1.1 Unalloyed/low alloyed
1	kg	Steel, low-alloyed {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for steel product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

Table 23. 1.1.2 “Highly alloyed”

1	kg	1.1.2 Highly alloyed
1	kg	Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for chromium steel product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

Table 24. 1.2 “Cast Iron”.

1	kg	1.2 Cast iron
1	kg	Cast iron {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

2 Light alloys, cast and wrought alloys

The VDA class 2.1.1 “*Cast aluminium alloys*” and 2.1.2 “*Wrought aluminium alloys*” have been modelled considering the alloy available in Ecolnvent and an average European manufacturing process for aluminium. While the generic class 2.1 “Aluminium and aluminium alloys” has been modelled assuming that 50% is made of aluminum and the rest of its alloys (of which 50% “*Cast aluminium alloys*” and the rest “*Wrought aluminium alloys*”) (see table below).

Table 25. 2.1 “Aluminium and aluminium alloys”.

1	kg	2.1 Aluminium and aluminium alloys
0.5	kg	Aluminium, primary, ingot {IAI Area, EU27&EFTA} market for Alloc Rec, U
0.25	kg	Aluminium, cast alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
0.25	kg	Aluminium, wrought alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for aluminium product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

Table 26. 2.1.1 “Cast aluminium alloys”.

1	kg	2.1.1 Cast aluminium alloys
1	kg	Aluminium, cast alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for aluminium product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

Table 27. 2.1.2 “Wrought aluminium alloys”.

1	kg	2.1.2 Wrought aluminium alloy
1	kg	Aluminium, wrought alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U
1	kg	Metal working, average for aluminium product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec, U

On the same line as Aluminum and its alloys, magnesium and magnesium alloys have been modelled: 2.2 “Magnesium and magnesium alloys” has been modelled considering 50% as Magnesium and 50% as magnesium alloy.

Table 28. 2.2 “Magnesium and magnesium alloys”.

1	kg	2.2 Magnesium and magnesium alloys
0.5	kg	Magnesium {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.5	kg	Magnesium-alloy. AZ91 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

No titanium is available in the components modelled for this vehicle; that is why the VD class “2.3 Titanium and titanium alloys” has not been modelled.

3 Heavy metals. cast and wrought alloys

In the vehicle under study copper is used within cables and boards. For this reason it has been modelled considering a dedicated dataset from EcoInvent: “Cable. three-conductor cable {GLO}| market for | Alloc Rec. U”. The functional unit of this dataset is expressed in metres. To convert length in mass, the conversion factor available in the metadata of the EcoInvent dataset has been used (1.04 kg/m).

Table 29. 3.1 “Copper” (e.g. copper amounts in cable harnesses).

1	kg	3.1 Copper (e.g. copper amounts in cable harnesses)
0.962	m	Cable. three-conductor cable {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 30. 3.2 “Copper alloys”.

1	kg	3.2 Copper alloys
1	kg	Copper {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
1	kg	Metal working. average for copper product manufacturing {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 31. 3.3 “Zinc alloys”.

1	kg	3.3 Zinc alloys
1	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 32. 3.4 “Nickel alloys”.

1	kg	3.4 Nickel alloys
1	kg	Iron-nickel-chromium alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Analysing the IMDS, it has been noted that the lead is used only in the battery. Since this component has been modelled *ad hoc* in a separate dataset. So there was no need to model the VDA 3.5 “lead”.

4 Special metals

Since no more detailed information on the class 4.1 “platinum e rodio” were available, it has been modelled assuming 50% platinum and 50% Rhodium. It has to be noticed that for specific use of these components (for example the platinum in the catalyst) will be used specific datasets. So this dataset has been used only when the component function is not available.

Table 33. 4.1 “Platinum/Rhodium”.

1	kg	4.1 Platinum/Rhodium
0.5	kg	Rhodium {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.5	kg	Platinum {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

To model the VDA class 4.2 “Other special metals”, the percentage composition of the components listed in table 21 has been obtained from a deeper analysis of the components containing this VDA class.

Table 34. 4.2 “Other special metals”.

1	kg	4.2 Other special metals
0.15	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.40	kg	Tin {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.01	kg	Cast iron {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.13	kg	Aluminium, cast alloy {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.24	kg	Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.02	kg	Silver {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0002	kg	Gold {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.045	kg	Nickel, 99.5% {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.015	kg	Copper {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
1.54E-5	kg	Lead {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

5 Polymer materials

Many polymers are included under the label “Thermoplastics”. To model this class, then, a more detailed analysis of the chemical composition of the components containing this VDA class has been done. I materiali polimerici sono costituiti da un mix di polimeri, per questo motivo si è resa necessaria un’analisi più dettagliata. The elemental composition of these components has been done through IMDS so to define the % of the different polymers that belong to this class. The injection moulding process to manufacture plastic has an efficiency of 0.994 kg of final product per

kg of material input. Thus polymers in granulate shape have been divided for this value in the dataset (see table below).

Table 35. 5.1 “Thermoplastics”.

1	kg	5.1 Thermoplastic
0.086	kg	Tetrafluoroethylene {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.15	kg	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.006	kg	Polyvinylchloride. suspension polymerised {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.038	kg	Polycarbonate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.008	kg	Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.517	kg	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.127	kg	Nylon 6 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.071	kg	Nylon 6-6 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
1.33	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Class 5.1.a contains thermoplastic resins reinforced with fibres.

Table 36. 5.1.a “Filled thermoplastic”.

1	kg	5.1a Filled thermoplastic
0.052	kg	Glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.745	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.744	kg	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.002	kg	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
1.51e-5	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0001	kg	Carbon black {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.028	kg	Propylene {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.028	kg	Ethylene. average {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0004	kg	Polyvinylchloride. suspension polymerised {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.151	kg	Talc (in ground)

Table 37. 5.1.b “Unfilled thermoplastic”

1	kg	5.1b Unfilled thermoplastic
0.276	kg	Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.090	kg	Polycarbonate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.191	kg	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.424	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.143	kg	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.009	kg	Polyethylene. low density. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.022	kg	Nylon 6-6 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.018	kg	Nylon 6 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.172	kg	Polyvinylchloride. suspension polymerised {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
9.354E-7	kg	Tetrafluoroethylene {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.081	kg	Polymethyl methacrylate. beads {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

0.001	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
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Classe 5.2 “Thermoplastic elastomers” contains copolymers with thermoplastic properties and elastomeric properties, that can be moulded through injection. Analysing the elemental composition of the components containing through IMDS, it was detected that to this category belongs mainly elastomers made of EPDM rubber (ethylene propylene diene monomer rubber) and polypropylene (PP).

Table 38. 5.2 “Thermoplastic elastomers”

1	kg	5.2: Thermoplastic elastomers
0.4961	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.4769	kg	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0191	kg	Polyethylene. high density. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.032	kg	Carbon black {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.001	kg	Tetrafluoroethylene {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.474	kg	Synthetic rubber {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Doing the same analysis through IMDS, it was obtained that the only components present in the VDA class 5.3: “Elastomers/elastomeric compounds” was the EPDM rubber. The EcoInvent dataset “Synthetic rubber {GLO}| market for | Alloc Rec. U” describe the manufacturing process of this exact type of rubber.

Table 39. 5.3: “Elastomers/elastomeric compounds”

1	kg	5.3 Elastomers / elastomeric compounds
1	kg	Synthetic rubber {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 40. 5.4 “Duromer”

1	kg	5.4. Duromer
0.650	kg	Epoxy resin insulator. SiO ₂ {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.107	kg	Phenolic resin {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.018	kg	Polyester resin. unsaturated {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.126	kg	Glass fibre {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.099	kg	Carbon black {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 41. 5.4.1 “Polyurethane”

1	kg	5.4.1 Polyurethane
0.5	kg	Polyurethane. rigid foam {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.5	kg	Polyurethane. flexible foam {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 42. 5.4.2 “Unsaturated polyester”

1	kg	5.4.2 Unsaturated polyester
1	kg	Polyester resin. unsaturated {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

A detailed analysis through the machine part containing the VDA class 5.4.3 “Others duromers”, allow us to define the elemental composition of this class. In the vehicle analysed in this study, to this label belong epoxy resins using a mix of aluminium oxides and silicon oxides. Thus, to model this category both the epoxy resins available in EcoInvent Database have been considered.

Table 43. 5.4.3 “Others duromers”

1	kg	5.4.2 Other duromers
0.176	kg	Epoxy resin insulator. Al ₂ O ₃ {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.176	kg	Epoxy resin insulator. SiO ₂ {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.647	kg	Phenolic resin {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Class 5.5 “Polymeric compounds” is not available, thus has not been modelled.

Table 44. 5.5.1 “Plastics” (in polymeric compounds)

1	kg	5.5.1 Plastics (in polymeric compounds)
0.433	kg	Polypropylene. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.433	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.29	kg	Glass fibre reinforced plastic. polyamide. injection moulded {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.29	kg	Polyvinylchloride. suspension polymerised {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 45. 5.5.2 “Textiles” (in polymeric compounds)

1	kg	5.5.2 Textiles (in polymeric compounds)
0.787	kg	Polyethylene terephthalate. granulate. amorphous {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.787	kg	Thermoforming. with calendering {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.214	kg	Nylon 6-6 {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.003	kg	Viscose fibre {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.001	kg	Phenolic resin {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

6 Process polymers

Class 6.1 Lacquers is available in very small quantities. The elemental analysis through IMDS showed that to this category belong mainly Alkyd resins and Acrylic resins.

Table 46. 6.1 “Lacquers”.

1	kg	6.1 Lacquers
0.5	kg	Acrylic varnish. without water. in 87.5% solution state {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

0.5	kg	Alkyd paint. white. without water. in 60% solution state {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
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Adesives have been modelled analysing the VDA subdivision of alla the adesived used in the vehicle provided by the manufacturer (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Composition of the adhesives used in the vehicle.

The EcolInvent dataset “Adhesive, for metal {GLO}| market for | Alloc Rec. U” describe well the adhesives composition.

Table 47. 6.2 “Adhesives. sealants”.

1	kg	6.2 Adhesives. sealants
1	kg	Adhesive. for metal {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

The elemental analysis shows that components belonging to class 6.3 *Underseal* are composed as reported in 29.

Table 48. 6.3 “Underseal”.

1	kg	6.3 Underseal
0.214	kg	Silica sand {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.452	kg	Acrylic acid {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.09	kg	Carbon black {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.244	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

7 Other materials and material compounds (scope of mixture)

Class 7.1 “*Modified organic natural material*” is very etherogeneous. Thus a deeper analysis of its composition through IMDS was necessary. The main components of this class are: Cotton, wool, cork, cellulose, paper, rubber and *backed cotton fibre*. The last one is a cotton based material woven

with synthetic materials (Polyacrylate PAK and Polyvinylidene chloride PVDC); a specific dataset has been created in SimaPro (see table below).

Table 49. Backed cotton fibre.

1	kg	Backed cotton fibre
0.65	kg	Cotton fibre {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.10	kg	Polyvinylidenchloride. granulate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.10	kg	Injection moulding {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.25	kg	Butyl acrylate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

The dataset for the class 7.1 has been the realized including the percentages of the aforementioned components obtained thourg IMDS analysis.

Table 50. 7.1 “Modified organic natural materials” (e.g. leather. wood. cardboard).

1	kg	7.1 Modified organic natural materials (e.g. leather. wood. cardboard)
0.0002	kg	Cotton fibre {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.013	kg	backed cotton fibre
0.004	kg	Cork slab {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.46	kg	Cellulose fibre. inclusive blowing in {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.457	kg	Sheep fleece in the grease {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0105	kg	Paper. woodfree. coated {RER} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0425	kg	Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene copolymer {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 51. 7.2 “Ceramics/ glass”

1	kg	7.2 ceramics/glass
1	kg	Flat glass. coated {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
1	kg	Tempering. flat glass {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 52. 7.3 “Other compounds” (e.g. friction linings).

1	kg	7.3 Other compounds (e.g. friction linings)
1	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

8 Electronics / electricis

Table 53. 8.1 “Electronics” (e.g. pc boards. displays).

1	kg	8.1 Electronics (e.g. pc boards. displays)
1	kg	Electronics. for control units {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Analysing the IMDS database, it was noticed that all the compnents belonging to the class 8.2 “*Electricis*” were electric cables. To model this calss, the ecoinvent dataset “Cable. three-conductor cable {GLO}| market for | Alloc Rec. U” has been used. Its composition reflects the IMDS

composition. The functional unit of this dataset is expressed in metres. To convert length in mass, the conversion factor available in the metadata of the EcoInvent dataset has been used (1.04 kg/m).

Table 54. 8.2 “Electrics”.

1	kg	8.2 Electrics
0.962	m	Cable. three-conductor cable {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

9 Fuels and auxiliary means

Table 55. 9.1 “Fuels”.

1	kg	9.1 Fuels
1	kg	Light fuel oil {RoW} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 56. 9.2 “Lubricants”.

1	kg	9.2 Lubricants
1	kg	Lubricating oil {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

A detailed analysis through IMDS database showed that the brake fluids are a mix of organic compounds. The two major compounds found have been used to model this dataset (see table below).

Table 57. 9.3 “Brake fluid”.

1	kg	9.3 Brake fluid
0.5	kg	Methyl tert-butyl ether {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.5	kg	Trimethyl borate {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 58. 9.4 “Coolant/ other glycols”.

1	kg	9.4 Coolant/ other glycols
1	kg	Ethylene glycol {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

Table 59. 9.5 “Refrigerant”.

1	kg	9.5 Refrigerant
1	kg	Refrigerant R134a {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

class 9.6 “washing water. battery acids” appears only in the vehicle batteries electrolytes. From IMDS it was obtained that the electrolyte is made of a mix of water (61.88%). Sulfuric acid (37.37%) and Sodium sulfate (0.75%).

Table 60. 9.6 “Washing Water. battery acids”.

1	kg	9.6 washing water. battery acids
0.374	kg	Sulfuric acid {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.619	kg	Water. completely softened. from decarbonised water. at user {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

0.008	kg	Sodium sulfate. anhydrite {RER} market for Alloc Rec. U
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Class 9.7 includes materials for metals protection, which is the zinc coating. The coat of Zinc is composed like this: 97.944% Zinc. 0.692% di Cromium(III); 0.64% di Carbon and 0.787% iron.

Table 61. 9.7 “Preservatives”.

1	kg	9.7 Preservative
0.979	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.007	kg	Chromium {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.014	kg	Cast iron {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

To the class 9.8 “*other fuels and auxiliary means*” belong other types of preservatives, mainly Trizinc bis(orthophosphate). Thus are modelled in the same way as the zinc coating aforementioned.

Table 62. 9.8 “Other fuels and auxiliary means”.

1	kg	9.8 Other fuels and auxiliary means
0.979	kg	Zinc {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.0069	kg	Chromium {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U
0.014	kg	Cast iron {GLO} market for Alloc Rec. U

1.1.2 Complex components

Complex components have been modelled with ad hoc dataset, and not as a sum of VDA materials. The materials composition derives from IMDS, while manufacturing processes have been obtained from literature. Since the sensitivity of these data for the manufacturer the modelled dataset can't be showed.

2 Life Cycle Impact Assessment

Impact assessment is reported for Cumulative energy demand according to the CED method; for abiotic depletion, abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), global warming (100a), ozone layer depletion, Photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication the CML baseline method (Guinée 2002) has been used, in the version updated in April 20013 (version 4.2). In the following tables the results of the analysis are presented.

2.1 Vehicle production

Table 63. Impact assessment of Diesel vehicle production. It includes components production. Manufacturing and intermediate transportation.

Impact category	UP1	UP2	UP3	UP4	UP7	UP10	Total
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	1.16E-01	2.41E-04	1.02E-01	3.52E-01	3.53E-04	1.82E-03	5.73E-01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	7.05E+04	3.94E+03	2.08E+04	1.76E+05	1.87E+04	9.00E+03	2.98E+05
Global warming (GWP100a) [kg CO ₂ eq]	6.65E+03	2.53E+02	1.55E+03	1.59E+04	9.97E+02	5.94E+02	2.60E+04
Ozone layer depletion (ODP) [kg CFC-11 eq]	3.52E-04	1.97E-06	6.51E-04	1.50E-03	1.86E-04	1.11E-04	2.80E-03
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	2.01E+00	4.55E-02	7.39E-01	1.03E+01	1.47E-01	9.73E-02	1.33E+01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	2.93E+01	1.44E+00	1.45E+01	2.15E+02	3.47E+00	2.31E+00	2.66E+02
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	1.38E+01	2.56E-01	5.61E+00	4.25E+01	7.74E-01	5.29E-01	6.34E+01
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	9.20E+04	4.82E+03	2.61E+04	2.26E+05	2.37E+04	9.91E+03	3.82E+05

Table 64. Impact assessment of CNG vehicle production. It includes components production. Manufacturing and intermediate transportation.

Impact category	UP1	UP2	UP3	UP4	UP5	UP7	UP8	UP10	Total
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	1.16E-01	2.41E-04	1.09E-01	2.29E-01	2.31E-03	3.53E-04	3.39E-04	1.82E-03	4.59E-01
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	7.05E+04	3.94E+03	2.08E+04	1.52E+05	2.25E+04	1.87E+04	1.67E+03	9.00E+03	2.99E+05
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	6.65E+03	2.53E+02	1.55E+03	1.37E+04	2.46E+03	9.97E+02	1.11E+02	5.94E+02	2.63E+04
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	3.52E-04	1.97E-06	6.08E-04	1.51E-03	1.67E-04	1.86E-04	2.06E-05	1.11E-04	2.96E-03
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	2.01E+00	4.55E-02	7.61E-01	4.36E+00	1.23E+00	1.47E-01	1.81E-02	9.73E-02	8.67E+00
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	2.93E+01	1.44E+00	1.51E+01	6.59E+01	1.59E+01	3.47E+00	4.29E-01	2.31E+00	1.34E+02
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	1.38E+01	2.56E-01	6.19E+00	2.80E+01	4.60E+00	7.74E-01	9.83E-02	5.29E-01	5.43E+01
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	9.20E+04	4.82E+03	2.61E+04	2.26E+05	2.37E+04	9.91E+03	9.91E+03	9.91E+03	4.02E+05

Table 65. Impact assessment of Electric vehicle production. It includes components production. Manufacturing and intermediate transportation.

Impact category		UP1	UP2	UP3	UP4	UP6	UP7	UP9	UP10	Total
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]		1.16E-01	2.41E-04	8.50E-02	1.18E-01	8.99E-01	3.53E-04	9.64E-04	1.82E-03	1.22E+00
Abiotic (fossil fuels) [MJ]		7.05E+04	3.94E+03	1.97E+04	1.17E+05	1.11E+05	1.87E+04	2.02E+04	9.00E+03	3.70E+05
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]		6.65E+03	2.53E+02	1.43E+03	1.02E+04	1.08E+04	9.97E+02	2.93E+03	5.94E+02	3.38E+04
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]		3.52E-04	1.97E-06	5.93E-04	1.04E-03	6.67E-04	1.86E-04	2.09E-04	1.11E-04	3.16E-03
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]		2.01E+00	4.55E-02	6.77E-01	3.00E+00	2.01E+01	1.47E-01	6.01E-01	9.73E-02	2.67E+01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]		2.93E+01	1.44E+00	1.31E+01	4.74E+01	3.61E+02	3.47E+00	1.90E+02	2.31E+00	6.48E+02
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]		1.38E+01	2.56E-01	4.61E+01	2.08E+01	5.57E+01	7.74E-01	4.91E+01	5.29E-01	1.46E+02
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]		9.20E+04	4.82E+03	2.46E+04	1.51E+05	1.57E+05	2.37E+04	3.26E+04	9.91E+03	4.95E+05

2.1.1 Components contribution

Table 66. Abiotic Depletion – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	kg Sb eq.	2.61E-01	2.61E-01	2.61E-01
Others	kg Sb eq.	9.54E-02	8.13E-02	3.00E-01
Engine	kg Sb eq.	9.48E-02	9.38E-02	-
Particulate Trap	kg Sb eq.	1.22E-01	-	-
7.3 Other Compounds	kg Sb eq.	-	-	2.33E-01
Electronic Control Unit	kg Sb eq.	-	2.04E-02	1.54E-01
Inverter	kg Sb eq.	-	-	8.27E-02
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	kg Sb eq.	-	-	1.89E-01
Total	kg Sb eq.	5.73E-01	4.56E-01	1.22E+00

Table 67. Global Warming – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	kg CO ₂ eq.	1.73E+04	1.73E+04	1.73E+04
Others	kg CO ₂ eq.	1.90E+03	1.74E+03	5.55E+03
1.1 Steels/Cast steels/Sintered Steels	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.21E+03	2.22E+03	7.71E+02
Axles	kg CO ₂ eq.	6.34E+02	6.34E+02	5.62E+02
Engine	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.03E+03	2.01E+03	-
CNG tanks	kg CO ₂ eq.	-	2.46E+03	-
Electrification Plant	kg CO ₂ eq.	-	-	2.72E+03
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	kg CO ₂ eq.	-	-	3.39E+03
Particulate Trap	kg CO ₂ eq.	1.91E+03	-	-
Supercapacitor	kg CO ₂ eq.	-	-	3.57E+03
Total	kg CO ₂ eq.	2.60E+04	2.63E+04	3.38E+04

Table 68. Photochemical Oxidation – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	4.81E+00	4.81E+00	4.81E+00
Others	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	1.69E+00	1.66E+00	3.95E+00
CNG tanks	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	0.00E+00	1.23E+00	0.00E+00
Engine	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	9.74E-01	9.64E-01	0.00E+00
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.25E+01
Particulate Trap	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	5.86E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
Supercapacitor	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	5.41E+00
Total	kg C ₂ H ₄ -eq.	1.33E+01	8.67E+00	2.67E+01

Table 69. Acidification – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	8.01E+01	8.01E+01	8.01E+01
Others	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	2.49E+01	2.34E+01	7.10E+01
Engine	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	1.46E+01	1.45E+01	0.00E+00
Particulate Trap	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	1.47E+02	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
CNG tanks	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	0.00E+00	1.59E+01	0.00E+00
Electrification Plant	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	1.89E+02
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	3.08E+02
Total	kg SO ₂ -eq.-	2.67E+02	1.34E+02	6.48E+02

Table 70. Eutrophication – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	3.24E+01	3.24E+01	3.24E+01
Others	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	1.24E+01	1.18E+01	2.41E+01
Engine	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	4.83E+00	4.77E+00	0.00E+00
Particulate Trap	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	1.39E+01	0.00E+00	0.00E+00
CNG tanks	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	4.60E+00	0.00E+00
Electrification Plant	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	4.89E+01
Electronic Control Unit	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	7.12E-01	5.37E+00
Inverter	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	3.02E+00
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	2.43E+01
Supercapacitor	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	7.52E+00
Total	kg PO ₄ ³⁻ -eq.	6.35E+01	5.43E+01	1.46E+02

Table 71. Cumulative Energy Demand – Components contribution

Components and materials	Unit	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Common processes and components	MJ	2.63E+05	2.63E+05	2.63E+05
Others	MJ	7.06E+04	4.09E+04	8.40E+04
1.1 Steels/Cast steels/Sintered Steels	MJ	2.12E+04	3.05E+04	1.32E+04
CNG tanks	MJ	0.00E+00	4.04E+04	0.00E+00
Electrification Plant	MJ	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	2.91E+04
Engine	MJ	2.72E+04	2.69E+04	0.00E+00
Na-NiCl ₂ Batteries	MJ	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	5.52E+04
Supercapacitor	MJ	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	5.01E+04
Total	MJ	3.83E+05	4.02E+05	4.95E+05

2.1.2 Maintenance

Table 72. Impact of the maintenance of the vehicle during its lifetime

Impact category	Diesel	CNG	BEV
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	6.64E-02	6.64E-02	1.81E-02
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	2.02E+04	2.02E+04	1.73E+04
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	9.96E+02	9.96E+02	7.32E+02
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	1.37E-04	1.37E-04	1.16E-04
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	4.89E-01	4.89E-01	2.15E-01
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	9.68E+00	9.68E+00	3.41E+00
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	1.63E+00	1.63E+00	9.57E-01
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	2.40E+04	2.40E+04	2.04E+04

Table 73. Impact of maintenance per km travelled (average mileage:240.000 km)

Impact category	Diesel	CNG	BEV
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	2.76E-07	2.76E-07	7.52E-08
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	8.41E-02	8.41E-02	7.22E-02
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	4.15E-03	4.15E-03	3.05E-03
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	5.70E-10	5.70E-10	4.84E-10
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	2.04E-06	2.04E-06	8.96E-07
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	4.03E-05	4.03E-05	1.42E-05
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	6.81E-06	6.81E-06	3.99E-06
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	1.00E-01	1.00E-01	8.49E-02

2.2 Use Phase

Table 74. Impacts of the Use phase – 1 km driven in the delivery mission M1.

Impact category	Energy carrier production			Direct CO ₂ emission			Other direct emission			Non-exhaust emissions			total		
	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	3.39E-08	1.86E-08	4.27E-07										3.39E-08	1.86E-08	4.27E-07
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	5.66E+00	7.50E+00	2.54E+00										5.66E+00	7.50E+00	2.54E+00
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	5.65E-02	6.95E-02	2.20E-01	3.13E-01	3.13E-01			6.71E-03					3.69E-01	3.89E-01	2.20E-01
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	7.28E-08	5.76E-08	2.51E-08										7.28E-08	5.76E-08	2.51E-08
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	3.56E-05	1.87E-05	4.64E-05				1.57E-06	1.45E-05		2.81E-05	3.16E-05	3.23E-05	6.53E-05	6.49E-05	7.88E-05
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	5.89E-04	2.22E-04	1.40E-03				1.98E-04	1.51E-04		7.01E-04	7.90E-04	8.08E-04	1.49E-03	1.16E-03	2.21E-03
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	7.37E-05	3.04E-05	3.50E-04				5.14E-05	3.92E-05		5.22E-05	5.88E-05	6.01E-05	1.77E-04	1.28E-04	4.10E-04
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	6.07E+00	8.34E+00	4.54E+00				0.00E+00	0.00E+00		0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	6.07E+00	8.34E+00	4.54E+00

Table 75. Impacts of the Use phase – 1 km driven in the delivery mission M2.

Impact Category	Energy carrier production			Direct CO ₂ emissions			Other direct emissions			Non-exhaust emission			Total		
	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric	Diesel	CNG	Electric
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	3.56E-08	1.91E-08	4.44E-07										3.56E-08	1.91E-08	4.44E-07
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	5.96E+00	7.71E+00	2.64E+00										5.96E+00	7.71E+00	2.64E+00
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	5.95E-02	7.14E-02	2.28E-01	4.02E-01	4.05E-01			6.71E-03					4.62E-01	4.83E-01	2.28E-01
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	7.66E-08	5.92E-08	2.61E-08										7.66E-08	5.92E-08	2.61E-08
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	3.75E-05	1.92E-05	4.83E-05				1.57E-06	1.45E-05		3.68E-05	4.03E-05	4.10E-05	7.58E-05	7.41E-05	8.93E-05
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	6.19E-04	2.28E-04	1.46E-03				1.98E-04	1.51E-04		9.20E-04	1.01E-03	1.03E-03	1.74E-03	1.39E-03	2.48E-03
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	7.75E-05	3.12E-05	3.64E-04				5.14E-05	3.92E-05		6.85E-05	7.50E-05	7.64E-05	1.97E-04	1.45E-04	4.40E-04
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	6.39E+00	8.57E+00	4.73E+00										6.39E+00	8.57E+00	4.73E+00

2.3 Complete LCA

Table 76. Complete life cycle. Impact per km travelled (240.000 km vehicle lifetime. use phase M1, Italian energy mix)

Impact category	Diesel - Operation	CNG - Operation	Electric - Operation	Diesel - Vehicle Production	CNG - Vehicle Production	Electric - Vehicle Production	Diesel - total	CNG - total	Electric - total
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	3.10E-07	2.95E-07	5.02E-07	2.39E-06	1.91E-06	5.09E-06	2.70E-06	2.21E-06	5.59E-06
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	5.75E+00	7.58E+00	2.61E+00	1.24E+00	1.25E+00	1.54E+00	6.99E+00	8.83E+00	4.15E+00
Global warming [kg CO ₂ eq]	3.74E-01	3.93E-01	2.23E-01	1.08E-01	1.10E-01	1.41E-01	4.82E-01	5.03E-01	3.64E-01
Ozone layer depletion kg CFC-11 eq]	7.34E-08	5.82E-08	2.56E-08	1.17E-08	1.23E-08	1.32E-08	8.50E-08	7.05E-08	3.88E-08
Photochemical oxidation [kg C ₂ H ₄ eq]	6.73E-05	6.69E-05	7.97E-05	5.55E-05	3.61E-05	1.11E-04	1.23E-04	1.03E-04	1.91E-04
Acidification [kg SO ₂ eq]	1.53E-03	1.20E-03	2.22E-03	1.11E-03	5.58E-04	2.70E-03	2.64E-03	1.76E-03	4.92E-03
Eutrophication [kg PO ₄ ³⁻ eq]	1.84E-04	1.35E-04	4.14E-04	2.64E-04	2.26E-04	6.07E-04	4.48E-04	3.61E-04	1.02E-03
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	6.17E+00	8.44E+00	4.63E+00	1.59E+00	1.68E+00	2.06E+00	7.77E+00	1.01E+01	6.69E+00

Table 77. Complete life cycle. Impact per km travelled (240,000 km vehicle lifetime. use phase M2, Italian energy mix)

Impact category	Diesel - Operation	CNG - Operation	Electric - Operation	Diesel - Vehicle Production	CNG - Vehicle Production	Electric - Vehicle Production	Diesel - total	CNG - total	Electric - total
Abiotic depletion [kg Sb eq]	3.12E-07	2.96E-07	5.19E-07	2.39E-06	1.91E-06	5.09E-06	2.70E-06	2.21E-06	5.61E-06
Abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) [MJ]	6.04E+00	7.79E+00	2.71E+00	1.24E+00	1.25E+00	1.54E+00	7.29E+00	9.04E+00	4.25E+00
Global warming [kg CO2 eq]	4.66E-01	4.87E-01	2.31E-01	1.08E-01	1.10E-01	1.41E-01	5.74E-01	5.97E-01	3.72E-01
Ozone layer depletion [kg CFC-11 eq]	7.71E-08	5.98E-08	2.66E-08	1.17E-08	1.23E-08	1.32E-08	8.88E-08	7.21E-08	3.98E-08
Photochemical oxidation [kg C2H4 eq]	7.79E-05	7.61E-05	9.02E-05	5.55E-05	3.61E-05	1.11E-04	1.33E-04	1.12E-04	2.01E-04
Acidification [kg SO2 eq]	1.78E-03	1.43E-03	2.50E-03	1.11E-03	5.58E-04	2.70E-03	2.89E-03	1.99E-03	5.20E-03
Eutrophication [kg PO4⁻⁻⁻ eq]	2.04E-04	1.52E-04	4.44E-04	2.64E-04	2.26E-04	6.07E-04	4.69E-04	3.78E-04	1.05E-03
Cumulative Energy Demand [MJ]	6.49E+00	8.67E+00	4.81E+00	1.59E+00	1.68E+00	2.06E+00	8.08E+00	1.03E+01	6.87E+00